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Deliverable 7.4

Summary and overall achievement of Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities

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1. Executive Summary

The objective of this report is to summarise the dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) activities implemented throughout the SEAMLESS project, assessing their impact where possible. The activities discussed in this report have been used to share information about the project and raise awareness amongst our identified target audiences (Copernicus Marine Service developers and users, academia, agencies and policy communities, early career oceanographer), of project outcomes relating to research and innovation, and prototype developments. The success of the DEC activities in being ‘impactful’ can be assessed by the number of audiences we have reached, engagement with them and the relationships built that will continue beyond the life of the SEAMLESS project. The vast majority of SEAMLESS communication activities have been executed as planned throughout the project, with only fairly minor adjustments, which were largely caused by the Covid-19 pandemic which affect the first 18 months of the project.

2. Scope

This report reviews the dissemination and communication activities utilised over the life of the SEAMLESS project with the aim to highlight the breadth and variety of materials produced, the audiences they have engaged and the impact they have had on audience groups. Activities in the project have been targeted to the needs of user communities and stakeholders, and included more targeted training to training the next generation and support the long term legacy of the products developed within SEAMLESS. It is expected that the disseminated materials remain available and useful beyond the project. The scope of this report is to take stock of where these efforts have already had success, and where future work might focus.

3. Introduction

Within SEAMLESS, communication activities aim to facilitate the exchange of information, ideas, and updates among team members, stakeholders, and relevant parties involved in the project. Meanwhile, dissemination and exploitation activities involved strategic efforts to share and leverage the results, outcomes, and knowledge generated by the project with identified target stakeholders.

This report underscores key activities and achievements in these three areas. Internal communication success was realized through team meetings, emails, and other internal channels supporting efficient information flow. Externally, communication was predominantly achieved through the website, social media, and electronic updates.

Dissemination concentrated on the planned and systematic distribution of project information to a broad audience, including stakeholders, researchers, policymakers, and the general public. Methods employed to disseminate SEAMLESS knowledge encompassed publishing research papers, conference presentations, participation of workshops (in particular those targeting the Copernicus Marine Service

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coordinator, developers and users), organization of training events, and maintaining an active project website and social media presence.

The exploitation of project results was effectively executed through the strategic roadmap outlined in D7.3. The roadmap outlines when monitoring and forecasting centres can incorporate new codes and algorithms for ensemble generation, assimilation, and ecosystem indicators. Once adopted, these new products will be accessible to the entire community of over 50,000 users.

The communication, dissemination and exploitation activities of SEAMLESS were developed following the strategy that were outlined in the SEAMLESS plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PEDCR; Deliverable 7.2). The objectives of the PEDCR were successfully met, as briefly summarized below:

Objective 1: External promotion of the SEAMLESS objectives and its aims at the start of the project to raise awareness and generate interest in its findings and products as these become available.

- External promotion of SEAMLESS objectives has taken place through the SEAMLESS website, twitter feed, and e-newsletter. Presentations have also been made at numerous on-line and in person events (see [events page](#) on website for examples) throughout the project. All outputs including access to code and training materials is freely available through the website.

Objective 2: Identification of external contacts and communication of the project's outputs and achievements to the contacts list, participant network and beyond.

- A GDPR-compliant database has been produced which identifies geographic areas of interest for each individual. A sign-up form was available on the website. Project outcomes and highlights were communicated outside of the project through this contact list, social media and through direct contact with user communities at conference and workshops.

Objective 3: Demonstrate and promote the SEAMLESS prototype and support its operational use across CMEMS.

The project's findings, the prototype (SEAMLESS Ensemble and Assimilation Tool: **EAT**) and the future research prospects have been communicated to interested stakeholders directly through hands-on training sessions both in person and virtually and through promotion and CMEMS events including working groups and the annual General Assembly.

Objective 4: Provide support for effective and productive communication within the project (with WP1).

- Internal communication has been effective while utilizing tools such as email lists, online meetings, Microsoft TEAMS, and face to face meetings for internal communication.

Objective 5: Evaluate the success of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

- This document provides the evaluation of this objective.

Objective 6: Deliver the roadmap to operational production of the SEAMLESS indicators in CMEMS.

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- SEAMLESS is detailing how Copernicus Marine Service can take up, and make the most of, our outcomes in a dedicated Roadmap that lays how and when the monitoring and forecasting centres could include the new codes and algorithms for ensemble generation, assimilation and ecosystem indicator delivery.

4. Internal communication tools

The Communication work package (WP7) has effectively established a robust framework to facilitate precise and targeted communication throughout the project. A dedicated email address (seamless@pml.ac.uk) was created to centralize communications, providing all project participants with an efficient channel for both intra-project and external communications. To further refine this approach, specialized email lists, such as those for Work Package Leaders and the Steering Committee, were implemented. These lists ensured that participants received project updates tailored specifically to their roles.

Utilizing the TEAMS content management (Figure 1) and sharing system played a pivotal role in project collaboration. Participants collaborated on reports, engaged in chat conversations, and effortlessly shared project documentation through this platform. Additionally, all project meetings were recorded, allowing for easy reference and sharing with those unable to attend.

Through these initiatives, the SEAMLESS project maintained streamlined, effective, and secure communication channels.

Figure 1 The TEAMS shared space, showing separate channels for different areas of work, chat posts, filing sharing and action log

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5. External Activities

Throughout the project, SEAMLESS established mechanisms to involve stakeholders, end-users, and network communities, highlighting the project's activities, findings, and products. The main avenues of communication include:

- SEAMLESS project website - <https://www.seamlessproject.org/>
- Social media platforms, largely X, formerly Twitter - <https://twitter.com/SEAMLESSproject>
- Face to face communication
- Workshops and presentations
- Electronic newsletter

Over the course of the project, SEAMLESS has used these tools to establish and sustain infrastructure engaging stakeholders, end-users, and the CMEMS community, effectively showcasing the project's achievements. This infrastructure was consistently maintained and enhanced during the project, adjusting to the project's results progression. The Communication Team held routine meetings to ensure its continued relevance in line with the project's activities. The PEDCR was followed from the start of the project, reviewed at the first periodic report in response to project developments and Covid-19.

All communication materials developed within SEAMLESS, as well as the website, share the same visual identity, with similar design features to create a unified and recognisable brand. Communication materials were developed in collaboration with relevant partners and all partners have been reminded to ensure materials state that the project received funding from the European Commission.

Some materials have been available since the first stages of the project, such as the website, whilst others were developed during the life of the project, including newsletter and training materials. Materials such as project reports, conference posters and presentations, newsletters, scientific publications and datasets have been reported through previous Periodic Reports. Further details on materials highlighted above are provide in the next sections.

Table 1 Overview of communication and dissemination materials

Channel	Visual Identity	Project documentation	Dissemination tools	Training materials
<i>Website</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Open repositories</i>		✓	✓	✓
<i>Social Media</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Events</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓

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5.1 Communication

5.1.1 Project logo and branding

The project logo and branding were established at the project's onset and informed all subsequent communication efforts. The logo can be accessed from the website and shared files in Teams. A PowerPoint template (Figure 2) was made available to project participants via Teams. This template was used at project meetings and were appropriate by partners giving external talks representing the project.

Figure 2 Title and Acknowledgement slide for SEAMLESS presentation template

5.1.2 Website

The SEAMLESS website (Figure 3) launched in January 2020 at <https://www.seamlessproject.org/> served as a comprehensive platform for dissemination project information and resources. Since its inception, regular updates including scientific highlights, software developments, events and training plans have been consistently incorporated. This platform is not just a repository for open access project information but has also functioned as the project's primary 'shop-front' emphasizing the project's highlights and promoting its products. The website's domain is guaranteed to remain active beyond the project's end, ensuring continued access to project details for at least five years post-completion (2028). While the website underwent continuous development throughout the project's tenure, it remains available for further enhancements as needed. Figure 3 provides some examples of pages within the website.

In terms of content and progression, the website has been dynamically updated following project developments, mirroring the project's trajectory. The main updates have involved:

- [SEAMLESS Prototype](#): this page has been updated and expanded multiple times through the project and highlights one of SEAMLESS key products and outputs. The prototype is an open-source user friendly tool (the Ensemble Assimilation Tool: EAT). The page describes what it is used for, how it was developed and provide links on how to access it. This section of the website provides:
 - links to GitHub where the EAT is publicly available – <https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/eat>.
 - Details of various training events
 - Tutorials

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- Generally useful links to related models: [General Ocean Turbulence Model \(GOTM\)](#), [Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models \(FABM\)](#), [Parallel Data Assimilation Framework \(PDAF\)](#)
- Community Networks: highlight the variety of networks and groups that SEAMLESS engages with and are part of.
- [For CMEMS and beyond](#): this section features key outputs relevant to the CMEMS communities and others including academics.
 - New and advanced data assimilation methods are shared through the [Data Assimilation Methods](#) pages.
 - Detail of relevant indicators that SEAMLESS can estimate provided via the [Controllability of indicators](#) pages.
 - [Top parameters](#) page highlights the importance of model parameters and explains how SEAMLESS ranked the CMEMS biogeochemical models used in the project.
- An [Events page](#) showcasing SEAMLESS's participation in diverse conferences, enriched with embedded links to our presentations as available.
- Outputs section provides a portal to project [public deliverables](#), [publications](#) and [general resources](#).
- Who's involved section provides details of project partners and researchers working on SEAMLESS, with contact information should any interested users which to get in touch to discuss work further.

From its inception in January 2021 to the end of the project (early December 2023), the website has tallied 1,732 distinct users (Figure 4) with over 5,490 page views (Figure 5). While a majority originated from associated European countries, a significant portion accessed from other regions, including the US, China, Canada and Morocco (Figure 4).

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Data assimilation methods

Through the SEAMLESS project new and advanced data assimilation methods have been developed for all CMEMS Marine Forecasting Centres (MFCs).

1 Global and Iberian-Biscay-Irish seas MFC

The current Global (GLO) MFC uses a SEEK filter with prescribed covariances to assimilate ocean colour in reanalysis simulations, which are also nudged to climatological nutrient fields. No biogeochemical analysis/forecast is performed with the GLO system and no biogeochemical assimilation at all is performed in the IBI system. In SEAMLESS, the Université Grenoble Alpes enhanced a stochastic ensemble-based system for the NEMO-PISCES model used in both the GLO and IBI MFCs. The system is based on 4D analysis with the LETKF for the assimilation of both altimetry and ocean colour data.

Table 3.1. Comparison of the CMEMS DA methods before (dark grey) and after recent developments (light grey) undertaken in the 3D MFC configurations, error covariance schemes, updated biogeochemical variables (PHY= phytoplankton, Chl = chlorophyll, N = nitrate, P = phosphate), and uncertainty estimation approaches.

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SEAMLESS EAT

SEAMLESS has developed an **open-source, user-friendly assimilative modelling tool**: SEAMLESS Ensemble and Assimilation Tool (**EAT**)

About

The core system of the prototype is a software made up of a 1-dimensional physical model coupled to five biogeochemical models and enabled with data-assimilation capabilities. The five biogeochemical models are used operationally in the Copernicus Marine Service, namely: PISCES, ERSEM, BFM, ECOSMO and ERGOM.

We have named to prototype EAT (SEAMLESS Ensemble and Assimilation Tool) (EAT) and it is publicly available on GitHub via – <https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/eat>. EAT will be continually developed over the next few years of the SEAMLESS project and the GitHub page will always have the authoritative version.

EAT builds on other software projects – notably General Ocean Turbulence Model (GOTM – <https://gotm.net>), Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models (FABM - <https://fabm.net>) and the Parallel Data Assimilation Framework (PDAF – <http://pdaf.awi.de>) and integrates these different components into a software product capable of doing data-assimilation simulations for any GOTM configuration where observations are available.

EAT will not only be a development platform for testing new assimilation methods and new biogeochemical models – but – also a production ready assimilation system for realistic 1D setups.

Realistic set-up are available for using the prototype straightforwardly in five data-reach sites in coastal areas, shelf-seas and open-ocean (stations BATS, L4, M, BOUSSOLE, Arkona) and with biogeochemical-Argo float transects.

The SEAMLESS prototype was been developed by BB and AWI. Its configurations by PML, OGS, UGA, NERSC and AWI.

Related links

[EAT \(SEAMLESS Ensemble and Assimilation Tool\)](#)

[General Ocean Turbulence Model \(GOTM\)](#)

[Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models \(FABM\)](#)

[Parallel Data Assimilation Framework \(PDAF\)](#)

EAT Training events 2023

-
- 16 Nov 2023** Workshop on ocean forecasting and its applications in the Mediterranean sea: present status, gaps and ways forward: Ensemble Assimilation Tool ("EAT") hands-on training session. In collaboration with [MonGOOS](#). Training slides [available here](#)

Figure 3 Screenshots of the SEAMLESS website, www.seamlessproject.org

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Figure 4 Geographical distribution of SEAMLESS website users (number of users)

Figure 5 Page Views of the most visited pages on the SEAMLESS website

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5.1.3 Use of Social Media

SEAMLESS utilized social media as a direct tool for engagement with the general public and stakeholders in related fields, expanding its reach, and increasing its follower count. This method provided consistent and up-to-date communication with the public, available on an informal platform and drawing viewership to the project's multiple communications platforms.

The SEAMLESS X account (former Twitter, Figure 6) was established at the start of the project. Being SEAMLESS a small-consortium and quite specialistic project, our group of followers did not grow rapidly initially. But as outputs and results grew in the second year our followers increased, standing at 68 at time of writing. Followers include a range of global academics, as well as stakeholders from our target user audience such as the Copernicus Marine Service, Ocean Predict, the European Marine Board, and POGO.

Twitter posts involved regular updates centred on SEAMLESS-related events, such as workshops, presentations at conferences and product releases.

SEAMLESS project participants have proactively tweeted from their personal accounts, integrating into the @seamlessproject handle, which has supported the viewership to the SEAMLESS Twitter. In the first year of the project, when work was focused on research development and the world was largely still in Covid-19 lockdown, there was more limited engagement. However, from 2022 when travel to conferences and workshops began and the project had information to share engagement grew. SEAMLESS has over 100 posts, including 34 unique tweets, the others being made up retweets.

Momentum grew in the final year of the project with 21 tweets receiving over 220 engagements which include likes and retweets. Figure 6 provides example of a SEAMLESS tweet.

Figure 6 Example of SEAMLESS tweet

5.1.4 Stakeholder Contact Database

To effectively distribute communication materials, SEAMLESS established a database of contacts with interest in the project's outcomes. Initiated during the project's early phase, the database was seeded with early SEAMLESS supporters, Advisory Board members, and existing relevant contacts the researcher's networks.

PML securely houses this data, compliant with the UK's Data Protection Act and the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; Regulation (EU) 2016/679). The system ensures contacts only receive

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relevant communications. Access to the database is restricted to project participants and is hosted on Teams.

A registration form has been available (Figure 7) since the project's launch in Jan 2021, 34 individuals have expressed their interest through the website.

Sign up for project updates

Enter your details below to be kept informed of project updates. We will use your data for this purpose only and it will not be shared with any third parties. Please read our [Privacy Notice](#) for further information.

Title:

Full Name:

Email address:

Organisation (if applicable):

Drop-down list:

Enter security code:

Figure 7 Form to register for updates

Community mailing lists

To increase the community of users of EAT and dissemination of SEAMLESS tools we shared information and links to code and Newsletter to the GOTM FABM, and PDAF community of users. This resulted in the SEAMLESS outputs being shared with over >500 potential users and interested audiences.

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5.1.5 Electronic Newsletter

The inaugural SEAMLESS newsletter, distributed in April 2023 (slightly delayed but strategically timed), delivered compelling results and updates to the stakeholder community. It featured noteworthy publications, SEAMLESS EAT advancements, and previews of upcoming training courses. Disseminated to the entire contact database and shared by partners across community networks, the newsletter served as a powerful tool for both internal and external communication. Crafted for broader audiences, it ensured all project participants were well-informed. The strategic use of concise headlines directing to detailed content on the project website not only enhanced clarity but also boosted website traffic, solidifying its status as a dynamic resource.

A final newsletter was released in December 2023 as a concluding news bulletin for the project, summarizing achievements and promoting the project’s successful end. The first edition had an 62% open rate, with 35% of these readers delving deeper through embedded links. By the latest edition (December 2023) this had risen slightly to 69% opening the newsletter and 41% of those reading further.

Figure 8 Screenshot of the first e-newsletter

5.2 Dissemination

5.2.1 Training and Tutorials

Over the course of the last year, SEAMLESS has been actively engaged in organizing and facilitating a comprehensive series of hands-on training courses on the EAT tool, which was finalized and documented in the last year of the project as planned. These training sessions were thoughtfully designed to cater to diverse audiences, embracing both in-person and virtual formats to ensure widespread accessibility. The training initiatives targeted various segments of the scientific community, with a notable presence at the 2023 CMEMS Annual General Meeting, where members of the CMEMS user community had the opportunity to explore the details of the SEAMLESS outcomes. Additionally, specialized courses were tailored for members of the Marine Ecosystem Analysis and Prediction Task Team (MEAP-TT) of the global Ocean Predict organization, contributing to the dissemination of knowledge within this specific domain. MEAP-TT is focused on developing the underpinning science and tools that will further the integration of biogeochemical and ecosystem models into existing ocean operational system and so is a key target audience for EAT.

Training Materials

The EAT source code is publicly available on GitHub (<https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/eat>) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10306435>). Ready-to-use versions for Windows, Mac and

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Linux are available via the widely used “conda” package management system (<https://anaconda.org/bolding-bruggeman/eatpy>). From the latter, EAT has currently been downloaded 908 times (summed over all versions and platforms).

Additional supporting training materials for EAT are provided through the project website including:

The [EAT video tutorial](#) (available through YouTube channel) demonstrates how to easily install the ensemble and assimilation tool EAT on a Windows and Linux system.

- Full recording on [online workshop](#) available; provides a general introduction to the project, detailed presentation of the EAT tool, associated uses and guidance for setting up.
- Presentations slides – details of the presentation given at training sessions is shared with participants and other interested users through the project website.
- Links to relevant suppositories and supporting materials: [General Ocean Turbulence Model \(GOTM\)](#), [Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models \(FABM\)](#), [Parallel Data Assimilation Framework \(PDAF\)](#)

Successful application and uptake of these materials can be measured through the follow up interactions project partners are having with users. Examples include:

- Student in Netherlands at the Wageningen Marine Research in the Netherlands using of the EAT in his research project.
- Researchers at Akvaplan in Norway using EAT.

Training the next generation

In the final year of the project SEAMLESS extended its educational outreach to students, exploiting the opportunity of the MonGOOS General Assembly and workshops, in Tangiers, Morocco, in November 2023. This training supported our goal of training the next generation of modellers giving them a deeper understanding of the SEAMLESS Ensemble and Assimilation Tool (EAT) and its application in the realm of biogeochemical ensemble data assimilation. This workshop had over 30 participants who are now trained in the application of EAT and can take it forward for broader use. Ongoing monitoring use and downloads of training materials show that students from this course have continued to use EAT and iGOTM after the conclusion of their workshop.

Use of SEAMLESS tools in studentships

The SEAMLESS data products and tools have been shared with and exploited in higher education by students. Notably directly in 2 PhD theses, one in Italy and the other in the UK.

Italy: Guido Occhipinti currently doing his PhD at OGS on stochastic biogeochemical modelling used FABM+BFM developed in SEAMLESS in his publication.

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UK: the SEAMLESS EAT tool has been used directly in a PhD by Leuan Higgs from Reading University (UK). He used EAT to test the feasibility of using Machine Learning (ML) along with data assimilation to deliver a substantial update to the operational system for UK regional seas biogeochemistry run at the Met Office. The ML update would enable the correction of many more of the ocean indicators than what is possible in the current system, a large part of this work is based on EAT.

“EAT has been extremely valuable in allowing me to set up experiments both efficiently and concisely. I have particularly enjoyed using the flexible plugin system that allows users to deploy custom code - which lets me test my ideas quickly.” Quote from Leuan Higgs, PhD Student, University of Reading.

Belgium: ENSDAM (see D3.1 - Code for ensemble evaluation in prototype) was used by a PhD student (supervised at Liège University and University of Grenoble), working on the development of the Black Sea MFC system as part of the CMEMS Tier-2 ODESSA project.

Estonia: PhD student at Taltech university in Estonia, based his work on the NEMO-PDAF code developed in SEAMLESS and provided to the BAL-MFC.

Overall, SEAMLESS training courses have been successful in help the project achieved its goal to expand the next generation of ocean modellers and data assimilators. They have also proved a highly successful way to engage with audiences and train user communities providing a hands-on experience that allowed participants to directly engage with the EAT tool and exploit the SEAMLESS science and technical innovations in ensemble BGC DA embedded in EAT.

In total, over 90 participants across these workshops gained practical insights and actively experimented with the tool's functionalities, exploring its capabilities in the context of data assimilation. By tailoring these training courses to diverse audiences and fostering direct interaction, SEAMLESS not only disseminates knowledge but also ensures that users across different scientific communities can harness the full potential of the EAT tool and SEAMLESS R&D in their respective fields.

5.2.2 Participation in events

Over the course of SEAMLESS partners have attended numerous events to engage with the broader community and share their project information. This includes participation in:

- > 25 conferences
- > 30 workshops
- Organisation of 2 workshops

Comprehensive information on all attended events is available on the website and in the two periodic project reports. However, here it is valuable to emphasize a few key workshops that underscore the project's commitment to achieving impact and fostering the uptake of results, particularly within the CMEMS user community.

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- Partners OGS, NERSC and UGA participated in the workshop on Coupled physical-biogeochemical Data Assimilation in November 2023 hosted by the CMEMS Biogeochemical data assimilation working group at the CMEMS General Assemble in Brussels, Belgium, in November 2023.
- OGS regularly attended the Copernicus Marine Service Ensemble Approach Working Group meetings e.g. April 2023 in October 2023
- PML and UGA participated in the Copernicus Marine Service Scientific and Technological Advisory Group meeting in November 2022.
- Representatives from SEAMLESS participated to the CMEMS General Assembly in 2021, 2022 and 2023.

Engaging in these meetings not only broadens networks but also initiates more in-depth discussions with potential users of the project's advancements. For instance, a noteworthy example is the proactive initiative taken by academic colleagues at the University of Grenoble Alpes (SEAMLESS partner) and at the University of Liege (SEAMLESS Advisory Board). They have been actively advancing SEAMLESS recommendations within the CMEMS Service Evolution ODESSA project, which encompasses the Black Sea Forecasting Centre—the sole MFC not directly developed in SEAMLESS. This collaboration underscores the ripple effect of our outreach efforts, expanding the application and influence of SEAMLESS recommendations across diverse domains, beyond the ones developed in the project.

5.2.3 Technical reports

The project deliverables served as technical reports and repositories for the developments and approaches produced by the project. Examples include: recommendations for weakly and strongly coupled physical biogeochemical data assimilation (D4.1 and D4.2), code for the SEAMLESS prototype (EAT; D2.1) and a report on the developments and experiments of joint satellite and in situ ensemble biogeochemical data assimilation performed in the SEAMLESS project, with recommendations to perform joint space-in situ data assimilation in the Marine Copernicus MFC 3D domains (D5.1). All technical reports are easily access through the project website <https://www.seamlessproject.org/Outputs/Deliverables> and have been published through Zenodo.

Their reach is tracked through views and downloads as show in Table 2. Project reports had an average of 62 views and 43 downloads. High impact outcomes include Observability of the target indicators in the 3D CMEMS MFC systems (D3.4), Report on the prototype BGC models and their 1D simulations in CMEMS MFC sites (D2.2) and Code for ensemble evaluation in prototype V2 (D3.1) all receiving over 60 downloads.

Table 2 Project reports with views and downloads from Zenodo. Sorted by publication date, most recent first.

Output	Type	Views	Downloads	Date
Recommendations for weakly coupled physical-biogeochemical data assimilation. D4.1 of project H2020 SEAMLESS (grant 101004032)	Report	42	31	July 2023
SEAMLESS prototype "ready-to-transfer" to CMEMS MFCs (D2.3)	Report	14	7	March 2023

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Guidelines on space-in situ data assimilation (D5.1). Deliverable report of project H2020 SEAMLESS	Report	41	28	February 2023
Observability of the target indicators in the 3D CMEMS MFC systems (D3.4)	Report	103	63	January 2023
Recommendations for strongly coupled physical-biogeochemical data assimilation (D4.2)	Report	44	36	December 2022
SEAMLESS: Report on the prototype BGC models and their 1D simulations in CMEMS MFC sites (D2.2)	Report	102	73	March 2022
Code for ensemble evaluation in prototype V2 (D3.1)	Code	107	64	October 2021
Code for stochastic parameterizations to generate ensembles in 1D or 3D MFC configurations (D3.3)	Code	44	39	February 2022

5.2.4 Peer Reviewed Publications

Academic exploitation of SEAMLESS outputs was achieved through the peer-reviewed publication of new research (methodologies and insights), potentially leading to future uptake of SEAMLESS products by the broad biogeochemical modelling and data assimilation community, by CMEMS and ultimately applied by the CMEMS user community. Eight papers within the scope and acknowledging SEAMLESS were published by the partners over the course of the project (Table 3), with others still in the pipeline. Peer-reviewed research is pivotal to provide transparency to Copernicus Marine Service and potential end-users on the methods developed during the project. Citation scores are increasing, especially with the older papers, this provides a measure of the usefulness and potential impact of the SEAMLESS outputs. All research outcomes have been published open-source.

Table 3 Research papers attributed to SEAMLESS (with citation and download scores where available)

Title	Publication date	Citations	OA Type
Marine ecosystem models of realistic complexity rarely exhibits significant endogenous non-stationary dynamics. Occhipinti, G et al. 2023. <i>Chaos, Solitons & Fractals</i> , 175. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2023.113961	October 2023	0	Green
Chromophoric dissolved organic matter dynamics revealed through the optimization of an optical-biogeochemical model in the NW Mediterranean Sea, Álvarez, Eva et al, 2023. <i>Biogeosciences</i> , 15. DOI 10.5194/bg-2023-48	24 November 2023	1	Green
Biogeochemical Modelling, Bertino, L et al. In <i>Implementing Operational Ocean Monitoring and Forecasting Systems</i> , Chapter 9, (pp. 249 – 306). ETOOFS. E. Alvarez Fanjul, S. Ciliberti & P. Bahurel (Eds.), 2022. DOI: https://doi.org/10.48670/ETOOFS	1 July 2022	6	Green
A solution for autonomous, adaptive monitoring of coastal ocean ecosystems: Integrating ocean robots and operational forecasts. Ford D, et al. 2022. <i>Front. Mar. Sci., Sec. Ocean Observation</i> . https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1067174	19 December 2022	2	Green
		Downloads: 162	

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Biogeochemical Model Optimization by Using Satellite-Derived Phytoplankton Functional Type Data and BGC-Argo Observations in the Northern South China Sea. Shu C et al. 2022. Remote Sens. 14, 1297. https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14051297	7 March 2022	4 Downloads: 2249	Green
The impact of ocean biogeochemistry on physics and its consequences for modelling shelf seas. Skakala J et al. 2022. Ocean Modelling Volume 172, 101976. 10.1016/j.ocemod.2022.101976	April 2022	5	Green
Reanalysis in Earth System Science: Toward Terrestrial Ecosystem Reanalysis. July 2021. Reviews of Geophysics. Baatz R et al 10.1029/2020RG000715	30 July 2021	12	Green
Towards a Multi-Platform Assimilative System for North Sea Biogeochemistry. Skakala J et al, 2021. 10.1029/2020JC016649	20 February 2021	9	Green

5.3 Exploitation of uptake of SEAMLESS

5.3.1 Engagement with entrusted entity

SEAMLESS engaged with the entrusted entity of the Copernicus Marine Service, namely Mercator Ocean international, since the inception of the proposal. Initially, Dr Julien Lamouroux joined the SEAMLESS advisory board, because of his role in the development of the global forecasting system of Mercator, as well as his chairing of the biogeochemical data assimilation working group of the Copernicus Marine Service. Firstly, by means of this engagement, Mercator has been gaining first-hand, near-real-time information on the findings of SEAMLESS relevant to Mercator's operational systems for the global and regional seas (e.g., the SEAMLESS ranking of the PISCES parameters will be used as a reference for the generation of ensembles in Mercator). Secondly, SEAMLESS's alignment with CMEMS's strategy and developments was strengthened (e.g. about the CMEMS' ensemble plans), and guidance on CMEMS procedures and events was gained (e.g., on CMEMS paths from R&D to operation and CMEMS calendar of events).

At a later stage, the engagement Mercator/SEAMLESS engagement was doubled with the move of the former SEAMLESS coordinator (Ciavatta), in the new role of both Mercator's coordinator of biogeochemistry R&D and SEAMLESS' Advisory Board. This change favoured further SEAMLESS to be routinely exposed in the framework of Mercator's implementation of Copernicus Marine Service (e.g. presentations in the CMEMS Science and Technology Steering Committee hosted at Mercator, and in Mercator's presentations at high-level events, such as the EC DEFIS Workshop on Copernicus & Biodiversity, Digital Twins of the Ocean forums etc).

5.3.2 Engagement with Copernicus Marine Service groups

SEAMLESS partners demonstrate a proactive and dynamic engagement with multiple Copernicus Marine Service groups, fostering deep connections within the broader community. Their active involvement serves as a cornerstone for championing SEAMLESS outputs and developments among

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our targeted user audience. This strategic positioning not only ensures heightened visibility but also facilitates an ongoing and robust dialogue with the Copernicus Marine Service. By actively sharing insights and advancements, our partners play a pivotal role in fostering an environment of collaboration and knowledge exchange, ultimately contributing to the sustained uptake and utilization of SEAMLESS innovations within the Copernicus Marine Service.

Groups SEAMLESS partners are actively engaged with include:

- Copernicus Marine Service PQ Working Group
- Copernicus Marine Service BGC-DA Working Group
- Copernicus Marine Service Ensemble Approach Working Group
- Copernicus Marine Service Scientific and Technological Advisory Group

A more detailed account of the uptake by SEAMLESS products is provided in D7.3 SEAMLESS Roadmap.

5.3.3 SEAMLESS Roadmap

The SEAMLESS Roadmap provides a guide for the uptake of SEAMLESS results by the Copernicus Marine Service. The Roadmap ([D7.3](#)) published in December 2023 provides detailed summary of how project developments can be included in the pathway for future uptake in the European operational service. We are already aware that our dissemination and exploitation activities have led to the successful inclusion of SEAMLESS outputs in the future plans of the Monitoring and Forecasting Centres. For example:

- In the Arctic: the PARSAC framework used in SEAMLESS has now also been used in the Arctic MFC to optimise the static parameters of the latest NRT ECOSMO-II forecasting system.
- In the Baltic: the MFC has already started to use the assimilation code including the new PDAF Observation Module Interface (PDAF-OMI) based on AWI in their test system (V. Huess, DMI, pers. comm., Design Review meeting Oct 2023), which is paving the way towards BGC assimilation with the same code.
- In the Mediterranean: The parameters optimized in SEAMLESS have been taken-up by the CMEMS MFC in their 3D OGSTM-BFM NRT system for the November 2023 Entry into Service.

Propositions for longer term uptake and impact are proposed in the Roadmap which cannot yet be evaluated as they related to the long term future of these products.

Full details of recommendations and plans across MFCs is provided in [D7.3](#).

6. Success metrics

To evaluate and measure the success of the SEAMLESS communication and dissemination activities a list of KPIs was developed at the start of the project. As demonstrated in Table 4 SEAMLESS has met and exceeded its planned KPIs in all areas. Most notably in the external events such as workshops and conferences that project partners have attended and used as a key avenue to share and raise awareness of the SEAMLESS products across our key target audiences.

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Table 4 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) targets for dissemination of scientific and technical results

KPI	Expected value by end of SEAMLESS	KPI status at end of Yr 1	KPI status at end of Yr 3
Activities linked to the project			
Number of academic journal peer-reviewed publications (GOLD open access)	15	4	8 (with 5 under review and 4 in preparation)
Number of non-scientific publications	1	0	1
Number of relevant international events attended (conferences, workshops, training events, other projects' meetings, etc.)	18	20	>55 - SEAMLESS partners >65 - In total including MOi
Number of conference presentations (oral or poster)	10	9	>25
Number of project outcomes available as Open Source	1	3	18 includes peer reviewed and Zenodo publications/reports, git hub repositories
Number of followers on social media channels	50	34	68
Estimated number of entities and persons reached through dissemination and communication activities:			
Number of total entities engaged from SEAMLESS' stakeholders, end-users and networks	10		>90
Number of businesses	1 internal, 2 external		1 internal (BB)
Number of relevant EU Research and policy infrastructures	1		4 EC DG DEFIS, DG MARE, JRC, HADEA (PML and MOi on behalf of SEAMLESS)

7. Conclusion

The potential risks outlined in the original PEDCR did not materialise. A noteworthy success for the project was the participation in face-to-face workshops where SEAMLESS scientists could really discuss and highlight the benefits of the SEAMLESS developments directly to audiences that are likely to use them. The training programme provided an opportunity for the SEAMLESS team to work directly with

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potential future users and academics to help ensure the tools developed by the project will continue to be used after the project has concluded.

In summary, the SEAMLESS PEDCR's planned approach has proven successful in raising awareness about SEAMLESS and its outputs, while also ensuring that the products are well-positioned for continued use by the Copernicus Marine Service. The open-source EAT tool has received extensive publicity, and training initiatives for stakeholders and students have guaranteed its longevity beyond the project's duration.